

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL STATUS IN LINGUISTICS AND ITS STUDY

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Abstract This article provides information about the concept of social status, its definitions in sociology, psychology, and its main features. The essence of this concept has also been discussed in linguistics. Pragmatic, sociolinguistic views on the concept of social status, opinions on speech communication are described.

Key words: language, speech communication, social status, social role, sociolinguistics, pragmalinguistics, speech habit.

Introduction: It is known to everyone that linguistics is one of the oldest sciences, and the oldest sources provide valuable information about language, its nature, and units. Naturally, the source of linguistics research is language. And language lived and lives only and only in human society as its own means of communication. There can be no language without society and no society without language. While the fact that language is the social essence and the main means of communication is unanimously recognized by all linguists at all times, from ancient times until the 70s of the 20th century, the existence of language as a means of communication together with dozens of ethnic and socio-psychological factors remained out of the attention of linguists.

Linguists have singled out as a research unit of linguistics only those phenomena that occur as a whole in the process of communication and can occur only in the form of oral or written speech from communication units that are a set of ethno-psychological factors of language and engaged in their research and analysis. It is impossible to imagine communication without the interaction of members of society and their influence on each other without exchange of ideas (giving and receiving information).

Speech communication is one of the most common terms in pragmatics. The term "communication" is used in many cases to convey information verbally, that is, through words, linguistic means, and through non-verbal, non-verbal, non-verbal means (gesture, various signs, signs, symbols, symbols) and classified as verbal or non-verbal communication depending on the effect of one. Speech communication means joint and cooperative use of verbal and non-verbal means in the communication process.

This is the first characteristic of speech communication. Knowledge of language plays an important role in the growth of human worldview. Due to the expansion of the subject of linguistics, the internal concepts of the development of linguistics, the active penetration of logic, psychology, sociology, ethnography and other sciences into some areas of linguistics, the analysis of concepts belonging to several humanitarian sciences.

Main part: Some terms and concepts of sociolinguistics are borrowed from sociology and social psychology. In particular, the concepts of social status and social role arose at the intersection of psychology and sociology. We considered it permissible to refer to the definition of this concept in the dictionary "Dictionary of sociolinguistic terms".

"The position of a person in society, his permanent or temporary place in various social hierarchies that determines his interactions with other people in society." Also, according to the dictionary, the concept of social status can be distinguished as stable (girl, man, Chinese),

acquired (teacher, leader), situational (client, buyer). This concept is defined in other sources as follows. Social status is a comprehensive characteristic of a person that reflects a set of certain characteristics. Most of the social statuses are achieved by the person himself. Such statuses are called acquired statuses. Student status is achieved by successfully passing university entrance exams, champion status by winning a competition, and husband status by marriage. Any status consists of rights, obligations and normative treatment corresponding to it. In particular, the status of a student consists of attending classes, passing exams, doing internships, using the university library, etc.

The status of a professor-teacher consists of potential in a certain subject, certain pedagogical qualifications, scientific activity, participation in the department meeting, etc. From a person who has this or that social status, people around him expect a certain behavior that corresponds to this status. Such a standard, generally accepted situation is called a social role. More than one role can match a status. Most of the roles that are common to society have a special meaning in language: father, husband, son, classmate, neighbor, teacher, shopper, passenger, client, etc.

Every adult member of society should know how to behave in the process of fulfilling their roles. A large number of factors are determined by the social status of a person in society. It should be noted that the most common, historically determined criteria of social stratification are education, financial status, prestige of activity, etc.

Social status is the general position of a person among other people, it is the basis of the evaluative attitude of people towards themselves. This process is manifested through the specific social roles of a person, and social roles are determined by the activity, profession, position at work, place of any person, the presence of subordinates in society or the fact that he is subordinate.

All these aspects contribute to the totality of the forms of speech behavior of a person. According to the social status, which is directly reflected in the speech behavior of the person, the social status of the participants of the dialogue is divided into types such as equal and unequal. Equal social status is a person entering into communication with a person who does not differ from him in terms of class and other social aspects. Unequal social status is the interaction of persons with a significant social difference. In ancient times, the difference between superiors and subordinates can be cited as a vivid manifestation of inequality in social status.

The role of the quality of speech in society is great. Speech is an indicator of the educational criterion of social stratification. With its help, you can significantly simplify and facilitate the way up the career ladder, increase the quality of the amount of information delivered to the recipient. It is necessary to constantly develop speaking skills, because active vocabulary develops gradually.

It is very important to remember the rules of literary pronunciation, because speech is not just a way of transmitting information, it is a clear image that can tell absolutely everything about a person. Social status is a multifaceted characteristic of a person that reflects a set of certain characteristics. Although this concept has been studied to some extent in sociopsychology, it has not been studied separately as an object of linguistics, in particular, sociolinguistics.

Conclusion: It has only been noted in a narrow circle in scientific literature on sociolinguistics and pragmatic linguistics. Expanding the essence of this concept, strengthening it with the help of given examples is one of the tasks that should be done by experts in the field.

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